

Different ways of Seeing: An Analysis of *Jaane Jaan* (2023) through Mulvey's Gaze Theory

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Abstract

This article examines Sujoy Ghosh's film, *Jaane Jaan* (2023) through the theoretical framework of Laura Mulvey's gaze theory. *Jaane Jaan* is a murder mystery featuring in one of the most popular International platforms Netflix. The theory detailed in Mulvey's essay *Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema* (1975) critiqued Hollywood cinema and its portrayal of gender stereotypes. This article will try to analyse through cinematic form, character dynamics, and representational politics, the way in which the film is explored as a contemporary site where classical structures of the male gaze are both reproduced and destabilized. The article argues that while *Jaane Jaan* employs many conventions Mulvey critiques, it simultaneously introduces shifts in visual and narrative strategies that indicate the development of feminist film language.

Introduction

The discourses around gender stereotyping, representation and cinematic pleasure continue to resonate across global film cultures. Laura Mulvey's seminal argument that classical cinema aligns visual pleasure with the heterosexual male gaze remains an analytical cornerstone in feminist film theory. Although developed in relation to Hollywood films of the mid-20th century, Mulvey's framework offers a productive lens through which contemporary non-Western cinema can also be interpreted and interrogated. It is one of the most critical interventions in the discourses of gender representation in cinema.

Sujoy Ghosh's *Jaane Jaan* (2023), a Hindi-language adaptation of the Japanese author Keigo Higashino's crime thriller *The Devotion of Suspect X*, provides fertile ground for employing the idea of gaze. The film is also a crime thriller where the past of the protagonist is kept under shadow. By the genre itself the film suggests various kinds of gaze. The

protagonist, Soneeya aka Maya, changes her name and identity to cover up her past. However, the vulnerable victim protagonist does so only to protect her present and flee from her past. The protagonist, a victim of abuse by her husband who had sold her and forced her into sex work, fled from her husband with her daughter. She settled in Kalimpong with a changed name and as an owner of a café so that her husband is unable to trace her. However, the husband finds her, demands money and wants to take their daughter away from her. The murder of the husband by the protagonist and the subsequent taking up of the blame for murder by the neighbour is the plot of the movie. Naren Vyas, the mathematics teacher, a next door neighbour to Maya, silently admires her and becomes a passive onlooker and protector. Karan Anand comes for the investigation of the murder of Maya's husband and is attracted to her instead. The film intricately weaves gaze, voyeurism, romance, crime and psychological tensions but at its core lies an exploration of how bodies, particularly female bodies, are viewed, surveilled, and judged. The central characters, Maya D'Souza, Naren Vyas and Karan Anand are entangled in multiple forms of seeing which are moral, erotic, investigative, judgmental and self-reflexive.

Gaze happens to be a very important aspect of this film as much of the film captures characters watching each other. Central to this examination is the character of the protagonist Maya D'Souza, whose aestheticization, vulnerability, and agency intersect in ways that complicate Mulvey's binary of woman-as-spectacle and man-as-bearer-of-the-look. The film's layered deployment of voyeuristic, erotic, protective, and institutional gazes allows for a reconsideration of how gendered spectatorship operates in contemporary Indian cinema. Mulvey's argument centers on how cinema structures vision and desire. This article argues that *Jaane Jaan* both reaffirms and interrogates Mulvey's propositions. While Maya is portrayed through the aesthetic conventions of female spectacle, the narrative simultaneously complicates this positioning through agency, psychological depth, and the multiplicity of gazes deployed. In doing so, the film illustrates the relevance of Mulvey's theory in contemporary Indian cinema while exposing its theoretical limits.

Mulvey identifies three interconnected gazes, the camera's gaze analyzing how the film apparatus frames bodies and actions. The characters' gaze through how figures within the narrative look at one another and the audience gazes through the viewer's participation in the cinematic spectacle. Classical cinema aligns all three with male subjectivity. Mulvey introduces two forms of visual pleasure. Voyeuristic scopophilia which is the pleasure in watching an unaware subject and Fetishistic scopophilia which is the aestheticized, eroticized presentation of the female body. Women thus become 'to-be-looked-at' objects. Male characters drive plot and action, while female characters interrupt narrative flow by becoming spectacle. This reinforces patriarchal structures and spectatorship.

The Framing of Maya D'Souza: Aestheticization and Vulnerability

Maya's entrance in *Jaane Jaan* conforms to Mulvey's formulation. Her beauty is foregrounded before her narrative agency, and she is positioned as enigmatic and desirable. The cinematography employs long takes and registering gazes from male viewers, immediately

coding her as a figure of visual pleasure. She owns a local café where various kinds of people visit while her next-door neighbour Naren Vyas comes to catch a glimpse of her.

Maya's history of domestic abuse adds a second dimension. Her husband, Ajit sold her to a strip club and forced her to take up sex work. Maya, which was not even the character's real name, flees to Kalimpong hiding her real identity. She also flees for the protection of her teenage daughter, who would have the same fate if Maya continued to stay with her husband. Her victimhood marks her not only as desirable but also as vulnerable. Classical cinema often uses femininity and vulnerability to intensify scopophilic pleasure. However, in *Jaane Jaan*, the abuse is neither eroticized nor graphically displayed except for the encounter with the husband before his death. Both Maya and Ajit encounter each other physically just before Ajit is murdered by Maya. Throughout the rest of the movie, it is represented through indirect cues such as shadows and post-violence aftermath. This refusal to visualize violence reduces the risk of converting trauma into spectacle.

Narratively, Maya functions as the 'mystery woman', a classic trope where the female figure becomes a site of male investigation. Both Naren and Karan attempt to decode her intentions, aligning her with Mulvey's notion of woman as narrative enigma rather than narrative agent. And yet, Maya's decisions shape the plot in ways that subvert this classical constraint.

The Gaze of Naren Vyas: Voyeurism and Devotion

Naren's observations of Maya from his apartment echo traditional voyeuristic structures. He watches her while she remains unaware, placing the viewer in a similar position of surveillance. The film begins with Naren contemplating suicide but being unknowingly interrupted by the next-door neighbour Maya who has just moved in. That particular incident leads to Naren simply watching Maya as someone who had saved him from attempting suicide, though unknowingly. Yet his gaze is strikingly devoid of erotic intent. Instead, it is configured as protective, intellectual and emotionally restrained. He visited the cafeteria run by Maya everyday just to catch a glimpse of her. But he neither intended to strike up any conversation with her nor become too familiar with her. This marks a departure from Mulvey's model, wherein the male gaze is inherently tied to erotic pleasure. Naren, a mathematician, reads the world analytically. His gaze is thus coded as systematic rather than predatory. Watching becomes a mechanism of emotional connection, complicating Mulvey's assertion that the male gaze objectifies women primarily for sexual pleasure.

These moments echo Hitchcock's voyeuristic male protagonists. Especially in *Rear Window* where the male protagonist derives emotional and sexual energy by watching women from afar. Naren identifies with the spectator. He is passive in action but powerful through observation. Mulvey notes that voyeurism emerges from a safe distance, where the viewer can enjoy looking without engaging. Naren is precisely this type of spectator. He is not assertive, rarely attempts to claim Maya physically and his emotional world is constructed entirely around watching her. His gaze is obsessive yet devout, aligning with the novel's original structure of

'devotion'. But through Mulvey's lens, his devotion becomes a form of patriarchal surveillance disguised as love.

Naren's concealment of the crime and his eventual fate signal a self-negating orientation of the gaze. He watches to protect Maya rather than to possess her. This inversion demonstrates a contemporary shift in how male subjectivity and spectatorship are configured in Indian cinema.

The Gaze of Karan Anand: Investigative and Erotic

As a police officer, Karan embodies institutional power. His gaze is simultaneously disciplinary, representing the authority of the state; investigative, aiming to uncover truth; eroticized, shaping Maya as an object of flirtation.

His interrogation scenes framed through over-the-shoulder shots and sustained close-ups reveal how cinema merges professional scrutiny with gendered desire. Many sequences align the spectator with Karan's point of view, reinforcing traditional male gaze structures. His visual fixation on Maya, especially in domestic settings, reactivates Mulvey's idea that women serve as both narrative obstacles and aestheticized visual content.

Karan's gaze, which both seeks the truth of the crime as well as desires Maya reflects a classical motif. This reinforces Mulvey's claim that cinematic desire is tied to mastery and knowledge-seeking over the female body.

The Cinematic Gaze: Lighting, Framing, and the Architecture of Looking

Maya is consistently lit with soft, dispersed light that enhances her face and hair. This stylistic choice aligns with fetishistic scopophilia. In contrast, violence and masculine spaces (the police station, the streets) employ harder, high-contrast lighting, emphasizing realism over beauty.

One of the film's most-discussed scenes is Maya performing a sensual dance to the song *Jaane Jaan* a clever intertextual reference to the original 1970s song. This scene is designed explicitly as spectacle where the camera fragments her body through close-ups of her waist, arms, and neck. Slow motion and diffusion filters replicate Bollywood's glamorized erotic aesthetic. Karan watches her, positioned as diegetic spectators. This is quintessential Mulveyan cinema where the woman performs, the men look and the film aligns the viewer with the male gaze.

Even though the scene builds character and relationships, it remains a prime instance of how the film aestheticizes Maya's sensuality to produce scopophilic pleasure. Several key spaces serve as zones of surveillance such as Maya's apartment which is a site of concealment and exposure. Naren's apartment becomes a vantage point for silent watching. The café which is a public stage for gendered looking and the Interrogation rooms become the institutional sites where the female body becomes evidence. These spatial dynamics mirror Mulvey's

division between spectacle and action. Ghosh uses spatial design to emphasize looking. Naren often stands near doorways overlooking Maya's house. Karan's investigative scenes involve peering into hidden corners or watching her café routines. Maya feels the constant presence of eyes.

CCTV footage is employed to track the movements of Maya and her abusive husband. After the murder of her husband, Maya becomes the prime suspect. This is a literalization of Mulvey's argument that cinema institutionalizes the gaze as a mechanism of power. When Maya is on camera, she becomes evidence, her body is reduced to data, and her agency is diminished as the men analyze her movements. Though she is the prime suspect in the murder and Karan understands that something is not right.

Thus, surveillance technology in the film becomes an extension of patriarchal looking. The landscape and architecture of Kalimpong becomes a visual metaphor for surveillance, reinforcing Mulvey's idea that cinema positions women as objects to be looked at. The long shots are based on long alleys, winding roads on the hills and shots from outside the café. The film frequently employs reflective surfaces. These visual motifs symbolically fragment the female body and multiply perspectives, reinforcing the instability of the gaze. Maya is often shown through mirrors or glass, suggesting fractured subjectivity and heightened vulnerability.

Maya's Agentic Self: Subversion and Performativity

Despite her aestheticization, Maya is far from passive. She participates actively in the crime's concealment, collaborates with Naren, and makes strategic choices under pressure. Her decisions guide the narrative more forcefully than either male character, undermining Mulvey's claim that women primarily interrupt narrative progression.

Maya consciously performs vulnerability and composure in different contexts: With Karan, she adopts a posture of innocence, shaping how he reads her. With Naren, she allows emotional transparency. In public spaces, she navigates visibility to maintain anonymity.

Such performative self-presentation suggests a self-aware negotiation with the male gaze. The film's climax underscores Maya's agency. She recognizes Naren's sacrifice but refuses to be subsumed into a romantic or gratitude-bound narrative. Her autonomy remains central. Unlike many thrillers, *Jaane Jaan* avoids sexualizing or sensationalizing violence against women. The absence of graphic depiction shifts the audience's stance from voyeuristic consumption to empathetic engagement. The film invites the audience to participate in looking through Naren's and Karan's eyes while concurrently interrogating the ethics of such participation. This self-reflexivity aligns with contemporary feminist critiques that advocate for a more conscious spectatorship.

Multiplicity of Gazes

The film demonstrates that spectatorship in modern cinema is not monumental. The coexistence of non-erotic, erotic, institutional, and self-aware gazes challenges Mulvey's rigid

dichotomy. Maya embodies a new cinematic femininity which is capable, traumatized, self-aware, and emotionally complex. Such representations signal a shift from purely objectified images to hybrid subjects navigating visibility. While Mulvey's concepts illuminate many aspects of *Jaane Jaan*, the film's nuanced portrayal of male desire, female agency, and spectatorship indicates the insufficiency of a purely patriarchal framework. Feminist film theory today requires more intersectional, culturally grounded models.

Conclusion

Jaane Jaan simultaneously mobilizes and destabilizes Mulvey's gaze theory. On one hand, the film frames Maya as aestheticized spectacle, subject to voyeuristic and investigative gazes. On the other, it grants her narrative agency, emotional depth, and strategic control over her own visibility. Naren's desexualized, sacrificial gaze and the film's refusal to eroticize violence demonstrate a shift in how desire and spectatorship are rendered in contemporary Indian cinema.

The film thus exemplifies a transitional moment while classical structures of the male gaze continue to shape cinematic language, new configurations marked by ambivalence, self-reflexivity, and ethical awareness are emerging. *Jaane Jaan* becomes not only a genre thriller but also a commentary on the very act of looking, inviting spectators to question the power dynamics embedded in vision itself. The setting for the movie with its gloomy, misty, hilly setting of Kalimpong provide a perfect background for the murder. This again was a very obvious and predictable setting for a murder mystery right from its prototypes in the west to other Hindi and other regional language movies belonging to this genre. However, the point I want to emphasize in the context of this movie is the idea of gaze.

Gaze means looking at the other. The act of looking in cinema has myriad meanings, one is the look of the camera and what it captures and at another level is the look of the characters at each other and at themselves, especially how they see and envision themselves and each other. In the film the camera is fully focused on the characters and their movements. The way the characters are portrayed in a claustrophobic atmosphere also reflects the psychological condition of the characters. Maya, the female protagonist is running away from her past. She was attempting to create a simple life for herself and her daughter in the hills away from the shadows of her past life. Gazing at the past could be one way of reading the character. Another way would be to gaze at the present and see her running a local restaurant and maintaining a humble living.

Yet *Jaane Jaan* also offers moments of subversion such as when Maya's decisive violence against her husband, her strategic performance of femininity, and her manipulation of how she is perceived all provide counter-gazes that trouble patriarchal control. The film cannot be neatly categorized as either fully upholding or subverting Mulvey's gaze. Instead, it reflects the tensions of contemporary Indian cinema, balancing star glamour with psychological nuance, feminist themes with male-centered narrative structures, and audience expectations with stylistic experimentation. Through Mulvey's lens, the film becomes a case study in how

21st-century cinema still grapples with the power dynamics of looking, desire, and representation.

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